

REFLECTING ON THE MEASURE OF OUR HUMANITY: REVISITING THE IMPERATIVE OF HUMAN SOLIDARITY

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ABSTRACT: This article addresses the intersections of the COVID-19 pandemic and the imperative of human solidarity based on a shared humanity. It expands on the justification of human solidarity, our understanding of what it means to be human foundationally, and it allows creative envisioning of the imperative of human solidarity. It provides a deeper framework of the issue of justice. Justice not only in vaccines distributions but also in the right to be treated as full human beings. As such, justice becomes inseparable from equality and equity, dignity and freedom. All human beings are seen as possessing infinite value. No hierarchicalism and ontological stratification of society between superiors and inferiors.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, human solidarity, dignity, freedom, sacred identity

INTRODUCTION

The following reflection focuses on what we can call the first human right: the right to be human, to be related to as a full human being and be treated as such. This right is intrinsically connected to the imperative of human solidarity. This is especially true in times of pandemics, crises, global threats, natural disasters, societal upheavals and various challenges.

Regarding the concept of human solidarity, it has been stated that “The discipline of politics has been guilty of overlooking this ‘subjective’ element of community life, but recent works by Stjernø and Brunkhorst reflect a growing awareness of the theoretical significance of the concept.”² It has received a major emphasis at the United Nations as a key to

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2. Lawrence Wilde, “The concept of solidarity: emerging from the theoretical shadows?” First published February 1, 2007, research article. *The British Journal of Politics and International Affairs*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-856x.2007.00275.x>.

meeting the challenges of life's predicaments during a time of pandemic.³

Addressing leaders of the world's richest countries at the G20 summit, the UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres, referring to the COVID pandemic, said the following: "We need solidarity and cooperation. And we need concrete action now – especially for the most vulnerable."⁴

In reference to the distribution of the COVID-19 vaccines, the UN Secretary General said the following:

"The recent breakthroughs on COVID-19 vaccines offer a ray of hope. But that ray of hope needs to reach everyone. That means ensuring that vaccines are treated as a global public good – a people's vaccine accessible, everywhere. This is not a 'do-good' exercise. It is the only way to stop the pandemic dead in its tracks. Solidarity is indeed survival."

In the following, we will be exploring the moral foundation for human solidarity. But first, clarifications are in order.

1. THE NATURE AND SCOPE AND HUMAN SOLIDARITY

At the outset, it may be useful to specify what solidarity is not and expand subsequently on its true nature.

Solidarity is not condescendence from a superior to an inferior. It is not charity in the sense of giving of one's surplus. It is not aid wealthy nations share with developing countries that have been victims of resources plunder for centuries. An infamous example has been the partition of Africa at the Berlin Conference in 1884. Instability in the Congo region has been the price to pay for being rich in mineral resources but poor in the scale of human flourishing, indecent standard of living, food insecurity, political instability, and economic chronic imbalances.

Solidarity is not just compassion in the sense of being moved because of other peoples' predicament. Compassion is indeed part of what it means to be human. It is needed. But being human means more. Human solidarity means more as well.

ROOTS OF HUMAN SOLIDARITY: CONSCIENCE AS UNIQUE CHARACTERISTIC OF BEING HUMAN

3. The General Assembly, on 22 December 2005, by resolution [60/209](#) identified solidarity as one of the fundamental and universal values that should underlie relations between peoples in the twenty-first century, and in that regard decided to proclaim 20 December of each year International Human Solidarity Day. The sustainable development agenda is said to be built on global cooperation and solidarity. See (International Human solidarity Day. [un.org](#)).

4. António Guterres. "UN chief to press G20 for greater solidarity and support during pandemic" (G20 virtual summit, New York, 20 November 2020). <https://news.un.org/en/story/2020/11/1078192>.

Human solidarity has deep roots. It is motivated by a shared identity, a shared humanity and actuality a shared destiny. It is characterized by an embrace of the shared mystery of being human. This shared humanity goes beyond mere biological features, intellectual potential, emotional make up or the same socialized patrimony, lineage or heritage. It is part of a deep mysterious belonging to the realm of the spiritual, an irreducible spiritual dimension which escapes definitions and confinements.

Humans are unique by virtue of not just our rationality and our capability to feel and express emotions but by virtue of our spiritual dimension. Our deep roots transcend the observable. Our thoughts can't be seen. Moreover, our rationality explores the external world to make sense of what we see. There is something happening at that inner level of evaluation, of processing what we observe in the phenomenal world. Our conscience, our center for ethical valuation operates in the inner chambers of our being, where no one has access. But this is where are formed how we relate to all others. Every decision made is supposed to be born from that secret space that functions like an inner sanctum, a sacred space.

Precisely, our solidarity as human beings and with human beings is grounded and nurtured by the inner conviction that human beings are sacred, unquantifiable by materialistic means.

To state my core thesis, our shared sacred identity is the foundation of our human solidarity. The importance of freedom of conscience lies at this intersection.

Freedom of conscience functions like a sign, a constant reminder of the full humanity of every human person. It is critical to uphold, to promote and to protect this freedom especially in times of vulnerability, fragility, and widespread infections from viruses and pathogens.

With the above clarification, we can now postulate that the main reflection we would like to submit to your consideration is that the fundamental issue which undergirds the main challenges during a time of pandemic is the measure of our humanity.

The existential question of the meaning of our humanity is made more difficult to answer in light of the reality of social tensions due to discriminations based on racism, tribalism, ethnocentrism, casteism, classism, colorism, gender discrimination and any form or expression of supremacist ideologies.

It would be an unfortunate omission not to address the problem of disenfranchisement of minority populations in America, in Europe and

elsewhere. History has witnessed a chronic deficit in solidarity with people groups whose lands were annexed, whose resources plundered, whose infrastructures fragilized or destroyed all together.

As the results of centuries of subjugations and exploitations, and multiple violations of rights, the indigenous people of the Americas and black people and people of color (BIPOC) in general are more vulnerable. They have less access to health care. In the current health crisis, they are disproportionately affected by the virus. These populations present the highest rate of fatalities from COVID-19.⁵

How to think about religious freedom in such contexts? First, the issue of the right to safe living should be addressed. Solidarity in wishing people and putting in place healthy environments is a must. The effects of environmental racism in the form of the dumping of toxic waste are devastating to populations of poor regions of the world. But there is more in our own backyard.

“Existing preconditions some of which as in the case of populations of Southwestern United States are due to exposure to uranium mining and radiation causing health issues like bone cancer, kidney damage and lung cancer give people little freedom and protection from COVID-19 and other debilitating and deadly diseases. . . .

Many low-income persons are daily exposed to the virus for being frontline workers and care takers. , , ,

The viruses then spread more in contexts where disenfranchisements abound, in contexts where racist policies, discriminations, victimization of citizens have been perpetrated for generations. Prison populations and infections of black people tell a story of systemic racial profiling and discriminations to such an extent that experts talk about a new Jim Crow law.”⁶

Unquestionably, systemic, structural, and institutional racism stemming from the colonial era and its institutions has put at a disadvantage the populations that do not have the means, the health, the medical structures and tools to efficiently fight against physical fragility and vulnerability to

5. See Mental Health America, Mhanational.org. “The COVID-19 pandemic has disproportionately impacted communities of color in America. Racial and ethnic disparities in health care are known factors contributing to the higher morbidity and mortality among people of color, as compared to white Americans. These disparities have a dual impact – not only are they resulting in differences in the actual care and treatment that COVID-19 patients receive, but they also put people in BIPOC communities at higher risk of contracting COVID-19 in the first place.”

6. Siena Fouse, “An Ongoing Battle: Fighting the Impacts of Uranium Mining in Southwestern Indigenous Communities” *Eli.org*, Wednesday, June 24, 2020.

pathogens and deadly agents. What exacerbates the current situation for minority populations is the racialization of the one human family which makes it nearly impossible to establish social justice.

People are suffering and dying from a virus particularly vicious against people with preexisting conditions created by social inequality and inequity, environmental pollution, lack of adequate sanitation due to poverty.

TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS

Our overarching thesis is the belief that the first human right is the right to be human, that is to have one's full humanity recognized, respected and protected. This full humanity of every person should not be diminished in any way because of skin color, gender or functional social status. Such dispositions and practices based on prejudices are deeply detrimental to human solidarity.

One of the key distinctive characteristics of our humanity is not just consciousness but conscience, freedom of conscience and the necessity of freewill without which self-determination would always remain aspirational but never operational.

Therefore, advocating and working for a more just world is a good place to start. The respect of every person's conscience being paramount in this endeavor. But beyond respect which can be just a disengaged way of not being involved in finding ways to help others find their way to healing and wholeness. Solidarity demands more. A benevolent attitude towards all others is a sure path to genuine solidarity with the whole human family.⁷

The responsibility to solidarity with the whole human family, is expressed in the consensus of the UDHR. It is a solidarity not based on charity in the sense of helping the poor but on a constant conscientiousness of what everyone shares with the poor, the dignity of the human person regardless of social circumstances. The focus on rights may have somewhat overshadowed or eclipsed the sine qua none of human responsibility toward every other human being.

As poignantly stated, "The Categorical Imperative operates primarily to tell you what you mustn't do to other people, not what you should do for them." Therefore, the need to revisit and restore the core in what makes us human, the responsibility of solidarity with the whole human family."

7. Hilde Lindermann, "Standard Moral Theories from a Feminist Perspective," in *Ethical Theory: A Concise Anthology*, edited by Heimir Geirsson & Margaret R. Holmgren (Ontario, Canada: Broadview Press, 2018), 387.

What is at stake and one of the most pressing questions is the understanding and adoption of what it means to be human.

Archbishop Rowan William insightfully expressed this problematic as follows:

“If there is one great challenge for our day, it is the pervasive sense that we are in danger of losing our sense of the human.”⁸

What does it mean to be a human being? This is a complex question.

Restrictive definitions limit the responses to this fundamental question to the issue of belonging to a particular group, whether tribal, ethnic, cultural, philosophical or religious.

The trajectory of identifying, valuing, classifying, and separating, leads to cementing the segmentation of humans into stratifications into superiors and inferiors, thus, stripping part of the human family of their deeper human identity and dignity. Importance based on socioeconomic categorizations has become the norm around the globe, in nearly every society. But human beings cannot be wholly defined through the lenses of the economy.

The dehumanization of others takes the trajectory of exclusion from a construct, in fact, an arbitrary, nonuniversal norm one chooses to believe and to elevate to the status of reference of how to view and to measure others. From this premise, humans are theoretically and practically subjected to valuing, segmenting and dividing into racial categories, castes and classes, economic status and materialistic worth.

As a problematic consequence, the loss of the sense of the human has led to the legitimization of violence. It is the root cause of the various violations of human dignity, human rights and human sacredness. In this latter sense, it is sacrilegious to trample any human being’s dignity. Toxic relations are perpetrated from the loss of the sense of sacredness and of the infinite worth of every person.

In spite of the violations and transgressions of people’s integrity, consensuses have been achieved at international levels and ratified through declarations, statements, covenants and conventions. Racializing human beings reducing identity to perceived features transgress peoples’ deeper identity and weaken the needed dimension of solidarity, which is essential to peaceful coexistence.

The UNESCO statement of 1950 was a landmark statement to debunk the foundations of racist theories. It states at the outset that “Scien-

8. Rowan Williams, *Being Human: Bodies, Minds, Persons* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2018), 25.

tists have reached general agreement in recognizing that mankind is one: that all men belong to the same species, *Homo sapiens*.”

The United Nations Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination ratified on 20th of November 1963:

“Solemnly affirms the necessity of speedily eliminating racial discrimination throughout the world in all its forms and manifestations and of securing understanding of and respect for the dignity of the human person,

Convinced that any doctrine of superiority based on Racial differentiation is scientifically false, morally condemnable, socially unjust and dangerous, and that there is no justification for racial discrimination, in theory or in practice, anywhere,”

Reaffirming that discrimination between human beings on the grounds of race, color or ethnic origin is an obstacle to friendly and peaceful relations among nations and is capable of disturbing peace and security among peoples and the harmony of persons living side by side even within one and the same State,

Convinced that the existence of racial barriers is repugnant to the ideals of any human society.”

That is the current verdict of the world. But here there is a gap between the ideal and the real. Practically, the measure of our humanity is tested by how we view and relate to other human beings. The current reckoning against racism challenges ancient practices based on violence against other human beings. It attempts to restore the sense and practice of human solidarity. The pandemic of COVID-19 may be an opportunity to recreate the sacred bond of human solidarity.

CRITICAL QUESTIONS

The questions which compel us to think more carefully about the true embrace of one humanity are the following:

- Are there justifications for hierarchical segmenting, valuing of human beings?
- Are stratifications and divisions of humanity between superiors and inferiors legitimate?
- What about the construct of racial superiority or inferiority which nurtures most racist and supremacist ideologies? These segmenting and valuing are accompanied with contempt and disdain of human beings deemed inferior.

The root cause of much senseless suffering, dehumanizing practices of discriminating against human beings is the legitimization of violence and the demeaning and trampling of human dignity. This toxic legitimization of violence has a tendency to creep into instrumentalization of religions for conquest, colonization, empire-building and annexations of peoples' lands and resources.

In times of pandemic, the fracture of human society is exacerbated by the trampling of human dignity, the disregard of the sacredness of people's conscience, the violations of other peoples' full humanity, and subsequent multiform discriminations based on their alleged sub-humanity and second-class citizenship of part of the human family. There must be a better humanity. It could be that the pandemic can be an opportunity to reset the buttons and place human solidarity at the center of human interactions by virtue of a shared humanity.

Human solidarity is grounded on the mystery of every human being. Human beings are more than biological beings. We are even more than rational beings with remarkable intellectual faculties and capabilities. There is something about human beings that transcends our analytical skills and tools. Beyond our intellect and emotions there is an elusive aspect of humans that people variously designate as spirit, soul, human consciousness, spiritual awareness.

Matter is not all there is. The spiritual dimension inherent in every human person makes us connected to transcendence and endowed with dignity and nobility which calls for a solidarity upon which depends our very survival. The virus makes no difference. Even though one has to be vigilant about what story or stories the distributions of vaccines will tell. Human beings are interconnected. Therefore, the need to affirm and promote solidarity. This solidarity extends beyond humanitarian assistance. It includes respect, kindness, gentleness, patience, faithfulness, self-control for the sake of solidarity. These, in fact, according to the Apostle Paul, are part of the fruit of the Spirit (Galatians 5:22)

Human cultural distinctions can be highlighted as a richness and welcomed as a blessed diversity of the human family. Though often sidelined and stifled, the values of brotherhood and sisterhood and equality present in all world religions and world philosophies can be rediscovered and protected.

Recovering the sense of the human is critical to the healing of the wounds of human existence many of which were created by the various

historical transgenerational traumas from slaveries, the gulags, the genocides and the debilitating and deadly diseases that ravage indiscriminately people of all walks of life, especially people with preconditions disadvantaged by slavery, segregation, and systemic racism.

The era of crimes against humanity must cease. Impunity for the those who destroy life replaced by accountability, education, resocialization and reintegration into more human and humane not only of *modus operandi* (method of operation) but also of *Modus Vivendi* (a way of life).

Integrating a sense of solidarity with all the human family is the only way forward to recovering a sense of the human-based on human dignity, and a shared human identity and destiny. Consequently, wearing mask, social distancing, purposefully being mindful of other people's safety and wellbeing, become part of human solidarity. So is the sharing of intellectual property, vaccines surplus and logistical support for developing countries to reach autonomy, and self-determination for the good of people of the planet. After all, in an interconnected world, insecurity anywhere is a threat to insecurity everywhere.

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